

Organic Pesticides, Part XVIII* : Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of Fluorine Containing 2,5-Disubstituted Imidazo [2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole Hydrobromides

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A series of fluorine containing 2,5-disubstituted imidazo [2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole hydrobromides have been synthesised by the reaction of phenacyl bromides on thiadiazoles in presence of ethanol. These have been characterised and tested for their anti-fungal activity against *Fusarium roseum*.

A wide variety of biological properties are encountered in thiadiazoles which have been reported to act as hypoglycemic agents¹, bactericides²⁻⁵, virucides², fungicides^{6,7}, herbicides^{8,9}, allergy inhibitors¹⁰, sedatives and tranquilizers¹¹. These observations prompted us to synthesize a large number of thiadiazoles of the type I.

These 2, 5-disubstituted imidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole hydrobromides listed in Table 1, have been obtained by the condensation of fluorinated phenacyl bromides with 2-amino-5-substituted thia-

diazoles (Scheme I) as shown below :

The compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Fusarium roseum* by agar growth

TABLE 1—FLUORINE CONTAINING-2, 5-DISUBSTITUTED IMIDAZO[2, 1-b]-1, 3, 4-THIADIAZOLE HYDROBROMIDES

Sl. No.	R	Substituents Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃ -	3-Cl, 4-F	89	50	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrClFN ₂ S	11.98	12.08
2.	CH ₃ -	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	199	48	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ S	12.5	12.81
3.	CF ₃ -	2-CH ₃ , 4-F	123	45	C ₁₂ H ₉ BrF ₃ N ₂ S	10.7	10.9
4.	CH ₂ CH ₃ -	3-Cl, 4-F	84	58	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ BrClFN ₂ S	11.3	11.6
5.	CH ₃ CH ₂ -	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	210	53	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ S	12.01	12.28
6.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ -	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	83	53.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ BrFN ₂ S	11.45	11.79
7.*	(CH ₃) ₂ -OH-I	4-F	102	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ BrFN ₂ S	10.25	10.71
8.*	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃ -	4-F	98	59	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ BrFN ₂ S	10.86	10.34
9.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ -	3-CH ₃ , 4-F	132	56.5	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ BrFN ₂ S	10.63	10.94
10.*	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ -	4-F	110	56.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ BrFN ₂ S	9.69	10.0
11.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ -	3-Cl, 4-F	74	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrClFN ₂ S	10.13	10.99

* Ar=Naphthyl ring.

* Part XVII, *Agric. Biol. Chem. (Japan)*, (1977) 41, 543.

method and the percentage inhibition recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 2,5-DISUBSTITUTED IMIDAZO[2,1-b]-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE HYDROBROMIDES AGAINST *Fusarium Roseum*

Compound No.*	Concentration	Colony diameter	% Inhibition
1	1 : 1,000	4.5	35.7
	1 : 10,000	5	28.5
	1 : 1,00,000	6	14.2
2	1 : 1,000	4.5	35.7
	1 : 10,000	5	28.5
	1 : 1,00,000	5.5	21.4
4	1 : 1,000	Above 7	Nil
	1 : 10,000		
	1 : 1,00,000		
5	1 : 1,000	5	28.5
	1 : 10,000	6.7	7.1
	1 : 1,00,000	7	0
6	1 : 1,000	Above 7	Nil
	1 : 10,000		
	1 : 1,00,000		
7	1 : 1,000	3	57.1
	1 : 10,000	3.5	50
	1 : 1,00,000	5	28.5
9	1 : 1,000	6.5	7.1
	1 : 10,000	7	0
	1 : 1,00,000	7	0

* Compound Nos. are according to the Table 1.

The PMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Model R.B.-12) with TMS as external standard. All compounds have shown characteristic resonance signals at δ 8.0 ppm for CH-N proton. Besides, alkyl protons were observed between δ 1.5 to 3.4 ppm and aromatic protons between δ 6.8 to 7.6 ppm.

Experimental

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles :

These were prepared by the method of Chubb et al.^{1,2} by treating a reaction-mixture of aliphatic acid (0.06 mole), thiosemicarbazide (0.05 mole) and sulphuric acid (conc. ; 6.2 ml) at 80-90°.

5-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-2-(n-pentyl)imidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole hydrobromides :

A mixture containing 3-chloro-4-fluoro- ω -bromoacetophenone (0.005 mole ; 1.26 g), 2-amino-5-n-pentylthiadiazole (0.005 mole ; 0.75 g) and ethanol (95% ; 30 ml) were heated under reflux for 8 hrs and the ethanol distilled off. The residual product was crystallised from methanol and the recrystallised compound gave a single spot on TLC. m.p. 74°, yield 1.05 g (52%). Analysis : Found : N, 10.13 ; C₁₅H₁₆BrClFN₃S requires N, 10.39%.

Other 2,5-disubstituted imidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole hydrobromides, listed in Table 1, were synthesised in a similar manner.

Evaluation of Fungicidal Activity by Agar Growth Method :

The test fungus *Fusarium roseum* was grown on potato dextrose agar medium, in which a desired amount of fungicide was previously incorporated in 1,000 ; 10,000 ; 100,000 ppm concentrations. The control consisted of plane PDA plates inoculated with the pathogen. The linear growth at 25° was measured after 7 days. Percent inhibition was calculated according to Vincent's (1947) formula, which is as follows :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{\text{Diameter of control culture}}{\text{Diameter of treated culture}} \times 100$$

Results

Compound Nos. 5 and 7 showed no activity. Compound No. 8 has shown slight fungicidal activity against *Fusarium roseum*.

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